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Title: AROMA PROFILE DESIGN OF WINE SPIRITS: MULTI-OBJECTIVE OPTIMIZATION USING RESPONSE SURFACE METHODOLOGY

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Abstract: Developing new distillation strategies can help the spirits industry to improve quality, safety and process efficiency. Batch stills equipped with a packed column and an internal partial condenser are an innovative experimental system, allowing a fast and flexible management of the rectification. In this study, the impact of four factors (heart-cut volume, head-cut volume, pH and cooling flow rate of the internal partial condenser during the head-cut fraction) on 18 major volatile compounds of Muscat spirits was optimized using Response Surface Methodology and Desirability Function approaches. Results have shown that high rectification at the beginning of the heart-cut enhances the overall positive aroma compounds of the product, reducing off-flavors compounds. In contrast, optimum levels of heart-cut volume, head-cut volume and pH factors varied depending on the process goal. Finally, three optimal operational conditions (head off-flavors reduction, flowery terpenic enhance and fruity ester enhance) were evaluated by chemical and sensory analysis.

Highlights

- High rectification during head fractions improves flowery and fruity spirit aroma
- Optimal pH and distillation cuts depend on aromatic profile goal
- Sensory analysis shows good correlation between aroma descriptors and chemical data

1 **AROMA PROFILE DESIGN OF WINE SPIRITS: MULTI-OBJECTIVE**
2 **OPTIMIZATION USING RESPONSE SURFACE METHODOLOGY**

3

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16 **Abstract**

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18 safety and process efficiency. Batch stills equipped with a packed column and an internal
19 partial condenser are an innovative experimental system, allowing a fast and flexible
20 management of the rectification. In this study, the impact of four factors (heart-cut volume,
21 head-cut volume, pH and cooling flow rate of the internal partial condenser during the head-
22 cut fraction) on 18 major volatile compounds of Muscat spirits was optimized using Response
23 Surface Methodology and Desirability Function approaches. Results have shown that high
24 rectification at the beginning of the heart-cut enhances **the overall positive aroma compounds**
25 of the product, reducing off-flavors compounds. **In contrast, optimum levels of heart-cut**
26 **volume, head-cut volume and pH factors varied depending on the process goal.** Finally, three
27 optimal operational conditions (head off-flavors reduction, flowery terpenic enhance and
28 fruity ester enhance) were evaluated by chemical and sensory analysis.

29 **Keywords:** **wine spirits;** multi-objective; response surface; desirability; volatile
30 compounds; distillation strategies.

31

32 **1. Introduction**

33 One of the main challenges of the food and beverage industry is to obtain unique
34 products in an increasingly competitive market. In the case of spirits, new operating strategies
35 can aid to improve quality, food safety and efficiency of the distillation process. Batch
36 distillation is the most used technique to produce spirits, where the distillate is collected in
37 three consecutive fractions: head-cut (waste), heart-cut (product) and tail-cut (waste), to
38 obtain a product with minimum off-flavors and toxic compounds. Traditional systems, like
39 copper *Charentais* alembics (**French style**), produce drinks with high levels of volatile
40 compounds that enhance their genuineness, an important feature of distinctive alcoholic
41 beverages. However, alembics allow limited control of the distillation process to improve the

42 product. On the other hand, modern continuous columns are generally used to obtain spirits
43 with a neutral aroma, intended for flavoring or ageing. In the spirits industry, batch columns
44 (**German style**) represent an **intermediate** technique, which provides enhanced control of the
45 rectification by varying the reflux rate; however, these systems are slow to respond, severely
46 limiting the process flexibility. Many studies have reported the differences of the available
47 spirits distillation systems (Alcarde, Souza, & Bortoletto, 2012; Christoph & Bauer-
48 Christoph, 2007; Da Porto & Decorti, 2008; Madrera, Gomis, & Alonso, 2003; Porto, 2008).

49 An innovative experimental system is the batch packed column equipped with an
50 internal partial condenser that allows fast and flexible control of the internal reflux rate
51 (García-Llobodanin, Roca, López, Pérez-Correa, & López, 2011). This system has been
52 compared with a traditional alembic by distilling wine and other fermented agricultural raw
53 materials (kiwi, pear and grape pomace) showing significant differences (**Arrieta-Garay et al.,**
54 **2013; Arrieta-Garay, Blanco, et al., 2014; Arrieta-Garay, López-Vázquez, et al., 2014**). In
55 particular, high refluxes at early fractions removed acetaldehyde, ethyl acetate and acetal from
56 **the** heart-cut, which allows obtaining a **cleaner** wine spirit (Matias-Guiu, Rodríguez-
57 Bencomo, Orriols, Pérez-Correa, & López, 2016; Rodríguez-Bencomo, Pérez-Correa, Orriols,
58 & López, 2016). Although packed columns increase distillation times and are difficult to
59 control (García-Llobodanin et al., 2011), the variable internal cooling flow rate can quickly
60 adapt the rectification level; hence, the producer can modify the volatile composition of the
61 spirit throughout the process by specific operational strategies (Matias-Guiu et al., 2016).

62 The distillation of fermented beverages causes the reaction of several aroma
63 compounds such as terpenes (Baxter, Laurie, & Mchale, 1978; Bedoukian, 1986; Ohta,
64 Morimitsu, Sameshima, Samuta, & Ohba, 1991; Osorio, Pérez-Correa, Belancic, & Agosin,
65 2004), esters (Fischer & Speier, 1895), furfural (Mottram, 2007; Nakama, Kim, Shinohara, &
66 Omura, 2014; Yemiş & Mazza, 2012) and aldehydes (Kłosowski & Czupryński, 2006), which
67 undergo transformations in a hot acid media. It has been reported that the juice pH alters the

68 microbiological behavior during the fermentation, affecting the aroma composition of pear
69 and melon spirits (García-Llobodanin, Senn, Ferrando, Güell, & López, 2010; Gómez, Úbeda,
70 & Briones, 2008). However, there is no information regarding the influence of pH during the
71 distillation. Furthermore, the distillation behavior of each compound changes throughout the
72 process (Jouret, Cantagrel, & Galy, 1998).

73 The aim of this study was to determine operational conditions for a batch distillation
74 column with an internal partial condenser to obtain different specific organoleptic
75 characteristics for a Muscat wine spirit. Heart-Cut Volume (HTV), Head-Cut Volume (HDV),
76 pH (adjusted with sulfuric acid, a common technique used in marc storage (Lukić, Miličević,
77 Tomas, Radeka, & Peršurić, 2012)) and Cooling Flow Rate of the internal partial condenser
78 during the head-cut fraction (CFR) were considered to be the main operational factors. To
79 carry out the head-cut multi-objective optimization (18 compounds), Response Surface
80 Methodology (RSM) was **applied** by performing a Central Composite Design with face
81 centered axial points (Derringer & Suich, 1980). For the multi-objective optimization, the
82 Desirability Function Approach (Derringer & Suich, 1980) was used for the most relevant
83 volatile compounds of Muscat spirits. In addition, optimal strategies were sensory analyzed.

84 **2. Material and methods**

85 ***2.1. Central Composite Design (CCD)***

86 Design of experiments is widely used to unveil the impact of defined input process
87 variables (factors) on output process variables (responses). **The CCD is a type of design of**
88 **experiments consisting of a 2-level full factorial design (FFD) with a center point and axial**
89 **points (Montgomery, 2013). The FFD is a design that studies the effect of all possible**
90 **combinations of 2 or more factors at 2 levels.** Center point is an experimental run whose
91 factor values are the average of the two levels of the FFD factors; they are usually replicated
92 to estimate and improve the variance of the system. Axial points are experimental runs with

93 the same factor values as the center point, except for one factor whose value is at a given
94 distance (α) from the center point. Factor values are usually rescaled (coded): FFD points =
95 ± 1 , center point = 0, and axial points = $\pm \alpha$ (one factor) and 0 (the other factors). Thereby,
96 CCD results allow a statistical estimation of linear and quadratic effects on a given response
97 with a reduced number of experiments.

98 For this study, a 3-level-3-factor CCD with face centered axial points ($\alpha = 1$) and six
99 replicates of the center point was designed (20 runs). Factors were Head-Cut Volume (HDV),
100 pH and Cooling Flow Rate (CFR) of the internal partial condenser of the column. To
101 minimize the number of runs, the factor HTV (Heart-Cut Volume) was not considered;
102 however, HTV was considered with the RSM, since 2 heart cuts were obtained from each
103 experiment. Runs were ordered with a randomized 2-block design to enhance the reliability
104 and validity of the statistical analysis of the factor effects. Center point runs were randomized
105 with a 2-block distribution (10 random runs with 3 center point replicates for each block). A
106 blocking variable was included to reduce the impact of possible nuisance variables throughout
107 the experimentation period (2 month) (Montgomery, 2013). Table 1 shows all the
108 experiments in the standard and real order of runs with coded and experimental values of the
109 factors.

110 2.2. Wines

111 All experimental distillations were carried out at the Departament d'Enginyeria
112 Química of the Universitat Rovira i Virgili. The CCD distillations used a *Vitis vinifera*
113 "Muscat" wine (2015 vintage year), with an alcoholic strength by volume of 12.6 % (v/v) and
114 a pH of 3.20, which was donated by Dalmau Hermanos y Cía. Suc. S.A. (Tarragona, Spain).
115 The pH of the wine was adjusted before each assay with sulfuric acid solution 2.5 M (GAB
116 system, Barcelona, Spain) at three levels (3.20, 2.45 and 1.70) according to the CCD method
117 (Table 1). The pH levels were chosen with the intention of observing marked differences.

118 Optimal distillations used a *Vitis vinifera* "Muscat" (2016 vintage year) with an

119 alcoholic strength by volume of 11.5 % (v/v) and a pH of 3.20, as well as a *Vitis vinifera*
120 “Macabeo” (2016 vintage year) with an alcoholic strength by volume of 10.6 % (v/v) and a
121 pH of 2.95. Both wines were donated by Cooperativa de Vila-rodona (Vila-rodona,
122 Tarragona, Spain). Their alcoholic strengths by volume were adjusted to 12.6 % (v/v) with
123 food grade ethanol of 95 % (v/v) (Droguería Boter SL, Badalona, Spain). According to the
124 optimal conditions obtained with the study of Muscat wine (2015 vintage year), the wines’ pH
125 levels were adjusted before each assay with a sulfuric acid solution 2.5 M (GAB system,
126 Barcelona, Spain) or sodium hydroxide solution 2.5 M (Sigma-Aldrich; Saint Louis, USA).

127 **2.3. Distillation System**

128 The distillation system (**Figure 1**) was scaled down from a 50 L pilot scale batch
129 packed column (García-Llobodanin et al., 2011) to a 1.5 L glass laboratory scale. A Florence
130 flask (2 L) was coupled to a packed glass column (filled with a 1.1 g copper mesh) and a glass
131 tubular heat exchanger (partial condenser). Both inner heat tubes had 8 mm of internal
132 diameter and 80 mm of length. The system was isolated and introduced in a fume hood at
133 constant recirculating air. The internal reflux was modified by changing the cooling water
134 flow rate (at 20 °C) of the partial condenser with a peristaltic pump (313S, Watson-Marlow
135 Ltd., Falmouth, England). The boiler was heated with a heating mantle (Fibroman-C 1000
136 mL, JP Selecta S.A., Abrera, Spain). Distillate samples were collected in 20 mL test tubes.
137 Test tubes were covered with perforated caps to minimize evaporation loss of the most
138 volatile compounds. In addition, the system was equipped with four temperature sensors: two
139 in the partial condenser system (shell outlet, T3; and shell inlet, T4), one after the partial
140 condenser (outlet stream of the inner tube, T2) and half a meter away from the device (fume
141 hood’s room temperature, T1). Before the experiments, the peristaltic pump of the partial
142 condenser was calibrated between 0 and 300 mL/min.

143 **2.4. Distillation Process**

144 **The 1.5 L** of wine was placed in the Florence flask with 3 g of pumice stone. The
145 electrical heating mantle operated at a constant power of 410 W during the first 33 min. Then
146 power was reduced and kept constant at 205 W until the end of each assay. Power values were
147 calculated without considering heat loss. Afterwards, to ensure reproducibility of the first
148 fraction, 300 mL/min of CFR was kept constant during 7 min to achieve total reflux. Power
149 and time values were defined after preliminary experiments (data not shown). **Then**, 40 min
150 (33 + 7 min) after the onset of the process, CFR was decreased to 100, 65 or 30 mL/min
151 during a HDV of 20, 12.5 or 5 mL according to the experimental design (**Table 1**). After the
152 first sample (S1), the partial condenser was stopped and emptied (CFR = 0 mL/min). The next
153 13 samples (S2-S14) of 20 mL each were distilled without CFR. The last sample (S14) had an
154 **alcoholic strength by volume** around 39 % (v/v). Optimal distillations were performed with
155 CFR and HDV values according to the optimal conditions obtained with the Muscat wine
156 (2015 vintage year).

157 **2.5. Chemical Analysis of Wine and Distilled Fractions.**

158 Wine ethanol content was determined by ebulliometry (**electronic ebulliometer, GAB**
159 **instruments, Moja-Olèrdola, Spain**), wine pH by a pH-meter (**Crison Basic 20, L'Hospitalet**
160 **de Llobregat, Spain**) and ethanol content of all distillation samples (S1-S14) by an electronic
161 density meter (**Anton Paar DSA 5000M, Graz, Austria**). Distilled samples were grouped in
162 four fractions: head-cut (S1), heart-1 (S2-S7), heart-2 (S8-S13) and tail-cut (S14). **A** 50 µL of
163 the internal standard solution (400 mg/L of 2-octanol, Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, **USA**)
164 were added to 1 mL of each fraction (**previously adjusted to an alcoholic strength by volume**
165 **of 40 % v/v**). All analyses were performed 21 days after each distillation.

166 **2.6. Chromatographic Analysis**

167 Chromatographic analyses were performed by using a gas chromatograph equipped
168 with a flame ionization detector (GC-FID) (**Agilent 6890, Agilent Technologies, Waldbron,**

169 Germany), an autosampler (Agilent 7683, Agilent Technologies, Waldbron, Germany) and a
170 capillary polar column (MetaWAX, 60 of length, 0.25 mm ID and 0.5 μm of phase thickness)
171 from Teknokroma (Barcelona, Spain). Injection (2 μL) was done in split mode (1:5). Injector
172 and detector temperatures were at 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 260 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively. Oven temperature
173 program was: 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (5 min), 7 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ up to 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (15 min), 3 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ up to 140 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 2
174 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ up to 200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (5 min). Column-head flow was initially set at 0.5 mL/min (28 min) and
175 increased with a rate of 5 mL/min² up to 1.1 mL/min (67 min) using helium as carrier gas.
176 Quantifications were carried out by interpolation into calibrations built with a synthetic
177 hydro-alcoholic solution (40 % v/v of ethanol) doped with all compounds at different levels.
178 Reagents' CAS, supplier companies and Kovats retention indices are shown in **Table S1**.
179 Detection and quantification limits were determined by Signal-to-Noise ratios (S/N) of 3 and
180 10, respectively.

181 *2.7. Response Surface Methodology (RSM)*

182 RSM aims to screen, model and optimize an experimental design by studying the
183 relationships between two or more independent variables (factors) and a response (compound
184 concentration). In addition to factors of CCD (HDV, pH and CFR of **Table 1**), the volume of
185 the heart-cut fraction was added to the model as a fourth factor. For that, the composition of
186 heart-1 (120 mL) plus a percentage of heart-2 (0 to 100 % of 120 mL) was considered as a
187 model response. The 0, 50 and 100 % of heart-2 (HTV) were the three levels chosen for the
188 RSM. It should be noted that the response variation produced by HTV is not necessarily
189 linear, since the concentration of the compounds (g/hL a.a.) depends on the alcoholic content
190 of both fractions (% v/v). In this way, the relative impact of distillation sub-fractions could be
191 evaluated. Therefore, after the CCD was performed, a 3-level-4-factor RSM could estimate a
192 second-degree polynomial model with all the compiled data.

193 *2.7.1. Response Surface Models*

194 In this study, sum-of-squares type III was used to calculate the error terms for

195 statistical significance of linear and quadratic main factor effects and the 2-way interaction
196 factor effects (Montgomery, 2013). Non-significant effects ($p > 0.05$) were ignored to obtain
197 more accurate estimation models. The RSM estimated response for each compound was
198 calculated using the following second-degree polynomial function with four factors:

$$\begin{aligned} 199 \quad \hat{Y} = & b_0 + \text{block1} + b_1 \cdot \text{HTV} + b_2 \cdot \text{HDV} + b_3 \cdot \text{pH} + b_4 \cdot \text{CFR} + b_{1,1} \cdot \text{HTV}^2 + b_{2,2} \cdot \text{HDV}^2 \\ 200 \quad & b_{3,3} \cdot \text{pH}^2 + b_{4,4} \cdot \text{CFR}^2 + b_{1,2} \cdot \text{HTV} \cdot \text{HDV} + b_{1,3} \cdot \text{HTV} \cdot \text{pH} + b_{1,4} \cdot \text{HTV} \cdot \text{CFR} + b_{2,3} \cdot \text{HDV} \cdot \text{pH} + \\ 201 \quad & b_{2,4} \cdot \text{HDV} \cdot \text{CFR} + b_{3,4} \cdot \text{pH} \cdot \text{CFR} \quad (\text{eq.1}) \end{aligned}$$

202 Where \hat{Y} is the estimated response for each compound (concentration in heart-Cut
203 fraction). *HTV*, *HDV*, *pH* and *CRF* are the coded factor values (± 1). *block1* is the blocking
204 variable; $b_{i,j}$ are regression coefficients whose subscripts stand for: 0 is the interception of the
205 function, 1 is the HTV, 2 is the HDV, 3 is the pH and 4 is the CFR.

206 As it has been introduced in **section 2.1**, adding a blocking variable to the model
207 allows us to minimize the effect of a known nuisance variable by arranging the experimental
208 runs in similar groups. In our case, we separate the experiments in two groups (blocks)
209 according to their order of execution. In sum, blocking **modifies** the origin of the coordinates
210 of a group of samples to minimize a nuisance variation, allowing a better fit of the relevant
211 variables of the study. **In this study, experiments 1 to 10 were used to determine $b_0 + \text{block1}$,**
212 **while experiments 11 to 20 were used to determine b_0 .**

213 **Therefore 40 experimental points were extracted from the 20 experimental assays,**
214 **because for every assay 2 heart fractions were analyzed (heart-1 and heart-2), specifically 30**
215 **data points (without counting central point replicates) and 16 regression constants (counting**
216 **the blocking variable).**

217 For compounds with low levels, concentration values below the detection limit were
218 considered as 0 g/hL a.a., and values between detection and quantification limits were
219 considered as the average of both limits.

220 *2.7.2. Desirability function approach*

221 Multi-objective optimization aims to calculate one optimal solution that groups several
222 objectives simultaneously. Derringer & Suich (1980) suggested transforming the estimated
223 responses (RSM) into a range of acceptability values between 0 (undesirable) and 1 (very
224 desirable). For optimizing, desirability functions are based on three response types: Nominal-
225 The-Best (NTB-type) to obtain a target value, Larger-The-Best (LTB-type) to maximize the
226 response, and Smaller-The-Best (STB-type) to minimize the response. A more detailed
227 mathematical explanation can be found in Costa, Lourenço & Pereira (2011).

228 Starting from the assumption that each compound has a positive or negative aroma
229 effect, LTB- and STB-type functions were used in this study. Curvature between inflection
230 points of the function was not considered. In order to transform the estimated response to a
231 linear desirability function, the following concentration points were used for each compound:

- 232 • Lower limit point: the compound odor threshold, assigned to a desirability value of 0 (for
233 the LTB-type) or 1 (for the STB-type). This limit was selected since it makes no sense to
234 do an organoleptic optimization of a compound **below** the consumer perception.
- 235 • Upper limit point: the maximum concentration analyzed in all CCD assays, assigned to a
236 desirability value of 1 (for the LTB-type) or 0 (for the STB-type).

237 Therefore, the individual desirability of each compound increased (LTB-type) or
238 decreased (STB-type) proportionally to the concentration range above the odor threshold, to
239 maximize or minimize the response according to its positive or negative odor effect on the
240 spirit, respectively. **Figure S1 (supplementary information) shows a graphical example of the**
241 **implementation of the desirability function in this study.** Odor **description**, desirability
242 function-type, odor thresholds and maximum concentration for each compound are shown in
243 **Table 2.**

244 To group several individual functions in a single multi-objective solution, Derringer &
245 Suich (1980) suggested obtaining an overall desirability by calculating the geometric mean of
246 the individual desirability of the compounds involved in each optimization. Thus,

247 optimization aims to find the values of the factors that maximize an overall desirability.

248 **2.8. Sensory Analysis**

249 Sensory analysis was performed in the tasting room of the Facultat d'Enologia of
250 Universitat Rovira i Virgili in compliance with standard NF V09-105 (AFNOR, 1987). The
251 training period was conducted in 14 sessions of 1 hour each with a selection of 17 assessors.
252 During training sessions, samples of ethyl alcohol of agricultural origin (40 % v/v) (Alcohol
253 Suave, Bodegas y Destilerías Lehman S.A., Tortosa, Spain) were spiked at several levels of
254 ethyl acetate as a Glue-like descriptor (0 to 300 mg/L range), linalool as a Terpenic descriptor
255 (0 to 12 mg/L range) and ethyl hexanoate as a Fruity descriptor (0 to 4 mg/L range).
256 Moreover, assessors were taught to differentiate spirits fractions by identifying the Tail-like
257 descriptor using tail cut fractions from spirit samples of a previous research (Matias-Guiu et
258 al., 2016) diluted at several levels.

259 For the sensory characterization of optimal distillation strategies (3 Muscat and 3
260 Macabeo), assessors scored samples using 4 aroma attributes (Terpenic, Fruity, Glue-like and
261 Tail-like) and a hedonic test, both using 11-point scales from 0 to 10. Two sessions were held
262 to replicate the analysis for each assessor, **using Latin square designs (Montgomery, 2013)**.
263 During the first 10 minutes of both sessions, assessors analyzed the optimizations produced
264 with the Muscat 2016 wine. Then, after 10 minutes of rest, Macabeo 2016 wine optimizations
265 were analyzed during another 10 minutes. For data analysis, the Product Characterization tool
266 of XLSTAT-Sensory statistical package was applied to check if the scores given by the judges
267 were significantly different (ANOVA model: Score = product effect + judge effect + session
268 effect). In both training and analysis, 5 mL of samples were served in black glass cups and
269 assessors had access to drinking water.

270 **2.9. Statistical Analysis**

271 **The CCD**, RSM and the Desirability Function Approach were performed with

272 STATISTICA 7.0 statistical package. ANOVA, Tukey's HSD test ($p < 0.05$), Spearman
273 correlation test, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Product Characterization (a
274 XLSTAT-Sensory tool) were performed with XLSTAT 2017 statistical add-in for Microsoft
275 Office.

276 **3. Results and Discussion**

277 **3.1. Center Point Analyses**

278 **3.1.1. Volatile composition of Head and Heart Fractions**

279 Center point (six replicates) was applied to analyze the distillation kinetics of volatile
280 compounds and their variance. **Table 2** presents the studied compounds (18 quantified
281 compounds out of 20 calibrated, showed in **Table S1**) grouped according to their distillation
282 behavior and physical-chemical characteristics (Cortés, Gil, & Fernández, 2009; Jouret et al.,
283 1998; Matias-Guiu et al., 2016). For all the studied compounds, the table includes their odor
284 descriptors, odor desirability function-type, odor thresholds, maximum levels found in all
285 assays of CCD and their concentration through the distillation of the center point.

286 In the center point, compositions of all compounds showed significant differences at
287 least between two fractions. Head compounds group (acetaldehyde, acetal and ethyl acetate
288 (C₂)) and fruity esters group (ethyl butyrate (C₄), ethyl hexanoate (C₆), ethyl octanoate (C₈)
289 and ethyl decanoate (C₁₀)) were mostly distilled during the head-cut due to their high vapor
290 pressure and/or high solubility in ethanol. In spirits distillations, the head-cut is implemented
291 to reduce the content of negative impact aromas (such as of acetaldehyde and ethyl acetate)
292 and toxic compounds (such as methanol) in the product (Christoph & Bauer-Christoph, 2007).
293 The C₄-C₁₀ ethyl esters are known for their high positive impact on spirits aroma, having low
294 odor thresholds and providing fruity notes (Christoph & Bauer-Christoph, 2007). Even though
295 methanol showed higher concentrations in the head-cut than in heart-1, it is not considered to
296 be a head compound, since it presented high levels in both the first and the last distillation

297 fractions (Carvalho, Labbe, Pérez-Correa, Zaror, & Wisniak, 2011) and its acceptance level
298 depends on its legal regulation (European Commission, 2008) rather than its aroma impact.
299 Acetic acid also showed high concentrations in the head-cut due to its formation by the
300 hydrolysis of ethyl acetate (Christoph & Bauer-Christoph, 2007), despite its high boiling point
301 (118 °C) (Environmental Protection Agency, 2012) and high water solubility ($K_{OW} = -0.17$).
302 Although, in the heart-cut it presented significantly lower values than its threshold.

303 The higher alcohols group (1-propanol, 1-hexanol, 2-methyl-1-butanol and 3-methyl-
304 1-butanol) and the terpenic compounds group (linalool and α -terpineol) tended to distill
305 during heart-1, due to their higher boiling point and/or solubility in water with respect to head
306 and fruity ester compounds groups. At high levels, higher alcohols are known for their
307 negative impact on the spirit's aroma (fusel-like flavors). In turn, terpenic compounds are
308 known for their high positive impact, providing the typical flowery notes from Muscat wines
309 (Christoph & Bauer-Christoph, 2007). In our distillates, some of the compounds of both
310 groups, like 1-propanol and α -terpineol, showed much lower concentrations than their odor
311 thresholds (**Table 2**).

312 Tail compounds (furfural, ethyl lactate and β -phenylethanol) distilled mainly in the
313 last fraction (heart-2), given their high boiling points and/or water solubilities. Tail
314 compounds are considered a defect in young wine spirits, especially furfural compounds that
315 give burned and sweet aroma notes. However, they can add positive characteristics to other
316 type of spirits, e.g. β -phenylethanol may provide a positive rose flavor and furfural may
317 contribute to toasted wood aroma (Christoph & Bauer-Christoph, 2007).

318 Methanol, recognized as a toxic compound, presented much lower concentrations than
319 the legal limit of 200 g/hL a.a. for wine spirits in all collected fractions (European
320 Commission, 2008). In addition, ethyl carbamate, a carcinogen compound of Group 2A
321 according to the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC Working Group on the
322 Evaluation of Carcinogenic Risks to Humans, 2010), was not detected in any fraction with an

323 analytical detection threshold of 0.2 mg/L (40 % alc. v/v).

324 3.1.2. System Variance

325 Traditionally, in the spirits industry, distillation columns do not operate at adiabatic
326 conditions and this hinders the production of distillates with consistent composition. In this
327 study, heat insulation significantly improved the experimental reproducibility of the
328 distillation runs. However, it was difficult to completely avoid or control external variables
329 with this distillation system (García-Llobodanin et al., 2011). The relative standard deviations
330 calculated from data of Table 2 for head-cut were high, especially for ethyl lactate (28 %),
331 ethyl octanoate (38 %), ethyl butyrate (40 %) and ethyl hexanoate (44 %). Nevertheless,
332 relative standard deviations in the compositions of the fractions that give rise to the product
333 (heart-1 and heart-2) were below 12 % in all compounds. The effect of room temperature and
334 distillation time on the composition of center point replicates was checked by simple
335 regression with no significant differences ($p < 0.05$) (data not shown).

336 3.2. Response Surface Analysis

337 Linear, quadratic and 2-way interaction regression coefficients, as well as adjusted
338 correlation coefficients of the model for the rescaled factors (eq. 1), are shown in Table 3. In
339 supplementary information, Table S2 shows other statistical parameters to measure the
340 goodness of fit of the models and Figure S2 presents contour plot examples that can help the
341 interpretation of the models, explained by regression coefficients of Table 3.

342 Some compounds presented a statistically significant lack of fit F-test ($p < 0.05$) due to
343 their low concentrations in heart-2 (C₄-C₆-C₈-C₁₀ ethyl esters) and heart-1 (β -phenylethanol)
344 fractions (Table S2). This can be explained because when the concentrations of the replicates
345 are around quantification limit, a large deviation is produced between analytical values above
346 the limit and those below; when the concentrations of all replicates are below the
347 quantification limit, replicates have identical or very similar concentration values, which
348 imply a pure error that tends towards zero. In both situations, the lack of fit F-test may be

349 significant. Therefore, in these cases, the goodness of fit is analyzed by the analysis of
350 variance of sums of squares (< 0.0001 for all models) and the adjusted correlation coefficient.

351 Blocking coefficients were significant in almost all models. Most volatile compounds
352 presented positive blocking coefficients (acetal and C₂-C₄-C₆-C₈ ethyl esters) except for
353 acetaldehyde. The remaining compounds had a negative coefficient, except for acetic acid,
354 which was in equilibrium with ethyl acetate. Thus, the system's rectification could change
355 through the days of experimentation by an unknown external factor that we could not control.
356 In supplementary information, **Figure S2** shows counter plot examples that can help the
357 interpretation of the models explained by regression coefficients of **Table 3**.

358 To clear up the following discussion of the effects of the studied factors on distillation
359 time during the head-cut, Tukey's (HSD) test pairwise comparisons after a multi-way
360 ANOVA ($p < 0.05$) were performed with head-cut distillation time (dependent variable) and
361 pH, CFR and HDV factors (explanatory variables). Significant differences were found
362 between 30 and 100 mL/min CFR levels and between all HDV levels. The pH showed no
363 significant effects. Thus, higher CFR (higher reflux) and higher HDV (larger head-cut
364 volume) increased distillation time (data not shown).

365 3.2.1. Distillation-cuts (HTV and HDV) Factors

366 As can be seen in **Table 3**, HTV and HDV linear regression coefficients of each
367 compound presented identical signs (+ or -) as long as both effects were significant, since
368 both factors depend on distillation kinetics previously explained in **section 3.1.1**.

369 Ethanol, head compounds, fruity ethyl esters and linalool tend to distill in higher
370 concentrations at the beginning of the distillation (Matias-Guiu et al., 2016). Hence, larger
371 HDV increased their extraction during the head-cut and consequently reduced their levels in
372 the heart-cut. In addition, since the concentration of these compounds in the boiler is
373 significantly reduced during the last fractions, a larger HTV dilutes them in the heart cut.
374 Consequently, both factors present negative linear coefficients. On the contrary, tail

375 compounds and α -terpineol tend to form and distill in later fractions of the process. Thus,
376 larger HDV increased their concentrations in the heart-cut because there is a displacement of
377 the tail cut, since heart-cut keeps the recovered volume, as well as an increase of the
378 distillation time. Likewise, larger HTV increased tail compounds levels in the heart-cut by
379 adding last distillation fractions. Therefore, both factors presented positive linear coefficients.
380 Higher alcohols and methanol presented no significant effects by HDV. The HTV negatively
381 affects the concentration of higher alcohols by dilution and depletion over time in the boiler
382 (Matias-Guiu et al., 2016) while methanol concentration is positively affected since its
383 relative concentration (g/hL a.a.) increases in the last fractions (Carvallo et al., 2011).

384 3.2.2. pH Factor

385 The distillation of wine occurs in an acidic hot environment with pH between 2.8 and
386 4.0 (Ribéreau-Gayon, Glories, Maujean, & Dubourdieu, 2006), and temperatures ranging
387 between 78 and 100 °C. This medium favors the formation or reaction of many volatile
388 compounds present in wine. Therefore, the pH of the raw material can be an essential factor
389 for plan distillation strategies, which, in turn, can be easily modified by the producer.

390 **Table 3** shows that all head compounds presented linear effects by pH, with a positive
391 regression coefficient for acetaldehyde and negative coefficients for acetal and ethyl acetate.
392 In acidic media, acetaldehyde and ethanol react to form acetal (Kłosowski & Czupryński,
393 2006). Furthermore, ethyl acetate is formed by acetic acid esterification, catalyzed in acid
394 media. Therefore, low pH accelerated the formation of ethyl acetate in the boiler (wine) and
395 increased its concentration in the vapor phase (product) since it is much more volatile than
396 acetic acid. Acetal and ethyl acetate also presented positive quadratic effects with pH,
397 showing lower levels in the 2.45 – 3.20 pH range. Hence, low pH favored acetal and ethyl
398 acetate concentration in the heart-cut and decreased acetaldehyde concentration.

399 In the case of fruity esters, their values were below their quantification limits in the
400 last fractions, due to depletion over time. For this reason, the sum of squares regression did

401 not find linear significant differences with pH, given the small variation of their concentration
402 in heart-2. Nevertheless, variations due to pH can be explained with 2-way interaction effects.
403 Fruity esters showed a positive coefficient of HTV-pH interaction for ethyl octanoate,
404 positive coefficients of pH-CFR interaction for all fruity esters, and negative coefficients of
405 HDV-pH interaction for ethyl butyrate and ethyl decanoate. Low pH could favor the
406 formation of fruity esters from their carboxylic acids, as happened with ethyl acetate – acetic
407 acid equilibrium, thus low pH favors removing fruity esters in the boiler due to their
408 formation at the beginning of distillation. Running out of these esters due to pH interaction
409 effects is more noticeable with high values of HTV and CFR (longer esterification time). On
410 the contrary, fruity esters exhaustion is reduced when the head-cut volume is small, since
411 there is a much shorter time for esterification (negative HDV-pH interaction coefficients).
412 Therefore, low pH accelerates the formation of fruity esters by esterification, behavior that
413 would decrease **their levels** in the spirit if the head-cut volume is too large.

414 In relation to tail compounds, ethyl lactate had a negative linear effect with pH, like
415 ethyl acetate. Even though pH should favor the generation of furfural during distillation due
416 to Maillard reactions (Mottram, 2007; Peña y Lillo, Agosin, Belancic, & Latrille, 2005;
417 Yemiş & Mazza, 2012), **this** effect was not significant.

418 Linalool and α -terpineol presented positive and negative linear effects with pH,
419 respectively, since linalool and other terpenic compounds tend to transform to α -terpineol in
420 catalyzed hot acid media (Baxter et al., 1978; Bedoukian, 1986; Ohta et al., 1991; Osorio et
421 al., 2004). Terpenic compounds also presented positive quadratic effects with pH, showing
422 lower levels in the 1.70 – 2.45 pH range. In the case of higher alcohols and ethanol, they
423 presented positive effects with pH, probably due to their reaction by esterification at low pH.

424 *3.2.3. Cooling Flow Rate (CFR) Factor*

425 Previous work had shown that high internal refluxes during the heart-cut can
426 significantly alter the distillation behavior throughout the distillation (Matias-Guiu et al.,

427 2016). The present study focused on head-cut reflux strategies; hence, CFR was applied
428 during the head-cut fraction only and in a narrow flow range to avoid masking the effects of
429 other factors.

430 Head compounds were efficiently removed during the head-cut with high CFR values,
431 due to their high volatilities and high solubilities in ethanol (Rodríguez-Bencomo et al.,
432 2016), and therefore showed negative linear effects with CFR.

433 Ethyl hexanoate showed a positive linear effect with CFR, indicating that high
434 rectification held up its distillation during the head-cut, favoring its recovering in the heart-cut
435 (Matias-Guiu et al., 2016). The C₄-C₈ fruity esters also showed pH-CFR and HDV-CFR
436 interaction effects. Positive pH-CFR coefficients indicate that high rectification avoids C₄-C₈
437 fruity esters distillation during the head-cut and slows down their formation by esterification
438 (at high pH). Negative HDV-CFR coefficients indicate that both factors slowed down the
439 distillation process and, consequently, increased the time for the esterification reaction during
440 the head-cut. Ethyl decanoate (C₁₀) presented the opposite effects with CFR and pH-CFR
441 coefficients, although its correlation coefficient was the lowest observed ($R_{adj} = 0.546$),
442 therefore analysis of these results should be done with care.

443 Linalool showed a negative linear effect with CFR, but a positive pH-CFR interaction.
444 High rectification increases the distillation time and therefore the degradation of linalool.
445 However, this effect diminished with high pH since it slows down the reaction (Baxter et al.,
446 1978; Bedoukian, 1986; Ohta et al., 1991; Osorio et al., 2004).

447 Higher alcohols and methanol presented a negative effect with CFR, except for 2-
448 methyl-1-butanol, indicating that high refluxes during the head-cut favored their recovery in
449 the heart-cut. Tail compounds were not affected by CFR, and acetic acid had the same
450 behavior as its ester form (ethyl acetate).

451 ***3.3. Multi-Objective Optimizations***

452 Desirability individual functions were constructed according to odor desirability, odor

453 threshold and the maximum levels found during the experimental distillations (**Table 2**). To
454 compute specific overall desirability functions, only compounds with a maximum
455 concentration above their aroma threshold were considered. Three optimizations were
456 calculated to obtain specific products with defined organoleptic characteristics: head off-
457 flavors reduction (acetaldehyde and ethyl acetate STB-type), terpenic enhance (linalool LTB-
458 type + acetaldehyde and ethyl acetate STB-type) and fruity ester enhance (C₄-C₈ esters LTB-
459 type + acetaldehyde and ethyl acetate STB-type). Acetaldehyde and ethyl acetate were
460 included in all optimizations to minimize organoleptic defects. Ethyl decanoate (C₁₀) was not
461 included in fruity ester enhance since it presented a considerably low fitting correlation
462 coefficient ($R_{adj.} = 0.546$). Results of the calculated optimal distillation conditions are shown
463 at the top of **Table 4**.

464 *3.3.1. Head Off-Flavors Reduction (HOR)*

465 This strategy should reduce the acetaldehyde and ethyl acetate contents in the heart-
466 cut. The largest HTV (240 mL) should dilute these compounds in the heart-cut, the largest
467 HDV (20 mL) should favor their recovery in the head-cut, the lowest pH (1.70) should
468 enhance acetaldehyde degradation, and the highest CFR (100 mL/min) should concentrate
469 these compounds in the head-cut.

470 *3.3.2. Terpenic Enhance (TEN)*

471 This strategy should significantly increase the content of linalool in the heart-cut.
472 Linalool is the only terpenic compound that showed concentrations above its aroma threshold
473 (**Table 2**) and the most important for Muscat spirits (Agosin, Belancic, Ibacache, Baumes, &
474 Bordeu, 2000; Cacho, Moncayo, Palma, Ferreira, & Culleré, 2013). Low HTV (16.7 %) should
475 concentrate linalool in the heart-cut, the largest HDV (20 mL) should clean the heart-
476 cut from **acetaldehyde and ethyl acetate**, the highest pH (3.20) should reduce linalool
477 degradation, and the highest CFR (100 mL/min) should reduce linalool loss in the head-cut.

478 *3.3.3. Fruity Esters Enhance (FEN)*

479 This strategy included operating conditions that, according to the models, would
480 enhance the fruity esters on the heart-cut. Medium HTV (66.7 %) should balance the
481 reduction of head off-flavors and fruity esters due to dilution, lowest HDV (5 mL) should
482 reduce their loss in the head-cut, high pH (2.95) should reduce fruity ester esterification, and
483 highest CFR (100 mL/min) would reduce losses of fruity esters during distillation of the head-
484 cut.

485 **3.4. Evaluation of Optimal Strategies**

486 Two different wines (Muscat and Macabeo of 2016 vintage year) were distilled with
487 the three optimal strategies to assess RSM models and to confirm chemical analyses with a
488 sensory panel. The main difference between both wines is that Macabeo wine is known for
489 having no detectable terpenic compounds.

490 **3.4.1. Optimums Chemical Analyses**

491 **Table 4** shows the predicted heart-cut composition of Muscat 2015 wine distilled with
492 the calculated optimal conditions (RSM). In addition, this table shows the mean concentration
493 of heart-cut, standard deviation and significant differences of Muscat and Macabeo 2016
494 wines distilled with the same optimal conditions.

495 Most of the times, the assessed strategies performed according to what was predicted
496 by the RSM models. Heart-cuts of both wines distilled with the FEN strategy showed in most
497 cases the highest values of C₄-C₁₀ ethyl esters. The TEN strategy applied to the Muscat 2016
498 wine yielded the highest levels of linalool and geraniol in the heart-cut. Geraniol was not
499 taken into account during RSM since Muscat 2015 wine and spirits showed geraniol levels
500 below its quantification limit. Macabeo had no detectable terpenic compounds in both spirits
501 and wine (data not shown). The HOR strategy showed the lowest values of acetaldehyde;
502 however, it also showed the highest values of ethyl acetate and unexpected high values of
503 other ethyl esters. As explained in **section 3.2**, we could infer from the RSM models that ethyl
504 esters increase with low pH; however, RSM models predict a decrease of their concentration

505 with high head-cut and heart-cut volumes, which has not observed in 2016 wine distillates. As
506 can be seen throughout **Table 4**, the rest of the compounds have a similar ratio of
507 concentrations between optimal strategies. Thus, deviation of ethyl esters in head off-flavor
508 reduction can be due to compositional changes of wines. Chemical analyses of the three initial
509 wines were carried out to understand this behavior (data not shown) without consistent
510 conclusions. **Furthermore, ethyl esters obtained low p-value in the lack of fit F-test, initially**
511 **attributed to their low levels in heart-2; therefore, the model may generate a wrong prediction**
512 **of the ethyl esters composition for the HOR strategy.**

513 *3.4.2. Optima Sensory Analysis*

514 Samples of the optimal strategies using both wines (Muscat and Macabeo of vintage
515 2016) were sensory analyzed by 17 trained assessors by rating Terpenic, Fruity, Glue-like and
516 Tail-like aroma descriptors, plus a hedonic rating test.

517 In order to reflect the aroma differentiation between samples, sensory data was
518 analyzed by PCA (**Figure 2**). Two principal components (PC1 and PC2) explained **93.6 %** of
519 the variance. Glue-like aroma was not included, as it presented no significant differences ($p <$
520 0.1). **The PC1** axis places Fruity and Terpenic aroma descriptors against Tail-like descriptor,
521 and PC2 places Fruity descriptor against Terpenic and Tail-like descriptors. This arrangement
522 in the biplot appears to be related with the compound groups associated to descriptors,
523 explained in **section 3.1.1**. The optimal strategies were well differentiated by PCA. Muscat
524 and Macabeo FEN samples presented high intensity of fruity aroma, and Muscat TEN sample
525 presented high intensity of terpenic aroma. Macabeo TEN sample was located near Macabeo
526 FEN sample, but with less fruity intensity. As expected, Macabeo spirits samples showed no
527 terpenic aroma. Muscat and Macabeo HOR samples presented high intensity of tail-like
528 aroma, since this strategy contained last fractions of the distillation to dilute acetaldehyde and
529 ethyl acetate in the heart-cut.

530 Finally, the preference test was analyzed with ANOVA and then Tukey's HSD test (to

531 check the acceptance between samples) and with the Spearman correlation test (to check the
532 correlation between aroma attributes and consumers acceptance). Hedonic data analysis can
533 only be taken into account as a suggested trend given the small number of assessors and their
534 previous training. Tukey's pairwise comparisons (data not shown) showed significant
535 differences ($p < 0.05$) between the Muscat TEN and FEN samples (highest ratings), and
536 Muscat HOR samples (lowest rating). Macabeo samples showed no significant differences.
537 Hedonic rating correlations ($p < 0.05$) showed that samples with terpenic and fruity aromas
538 were scored positively, and samples with glue-like and tail-like aromas were scored
539 negatively (**Figure S3**). This hedonic results illustrate how developing and implementing
540 distillation strategies can favor the production of genuine beverages that retain or enhance
541 flavors coming from the initial fermented beverage, like terpenes (grape origin) and fruity
542 ethyl esters (alcoholic fermentation origin).

543 **4. Conclusions**

544 High rectifications during distillation of the head-cut resulted in improved spirits,
545 characterized by low content of head compounds and high content of fruity and terpenic
546 compounds. The effect of distillation volumes and pH should be considered and adjusted
547 when different groups of volatile compounds are needed to optimize the results, depending on
548 which aromas should be enhanced or reduced. A larger heart-cut decreased all studied
549 compound levels, except tail compounds (off-flavors), α -terpineol (without odor impact at
550 spirit levels) and methanol (toxic compound). A larger head-cut decreased the concentration
551 of head compounds (off-flavors), at the cost of reducing C₄-C₁₀ ethyl esters and linalool levels
552 (positive odors) and increasing the level of tail-cut compounds (longer distillation time). Low
553 pH favored the decomposition of linalool and acetaldehyde to form α -terpineol and acetal,
554 respectively, and favored the formation of ethyl esters by esterification. Sensory analysis
555 corroborated the optimization of aroma compounds in spirits by chemical modeling using
556 RSM. These results reinforce the versatility of this experimental system and deepen its ability

557 to modify the aroma profile of spirit beverages.

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684

685 **Figure Captions**

686 **Figure 1.** Sketch of the distillation device. T1 to 4 are temperature sensors. Except for
687 T1, distances and dimensions between device parts were maintained using an original
688 drawing.

689

690 **Figure 2.** PCA biplot of the sensory profile of optimal distillation strategies (HOR,
691 FEN and TEN) using Muscat (Musc.) and Macabeo (Maca.) wines of 2016 vintage and
692 filtering the non-discriminant descriptors ($p < 0.1$).

1 **Tables**

Table 1. Central Composite Design 3-level-3-factor with face centered Axial Points (AP) and 6 Center Points (CP). Uncoded values are shown in brackets.

Run number	Run order	Head-Cut Volume (mL)	Cooling Flow Rate ^a (mL/min)	pH
1	2	-1 (5.00)	-1 (30.0)	-1 (1.70)
2	1	+1 (20.0)	+1 (100)	-1 (1.70)
3	5	+1 (20.0)	-1 (30.0)	+1 (3.20)
4	3	-1 (5.00)	+1 (100)	+1 (3.20)
5	12	+1 (20.0)	-1 (30.0)	-1 (1.70)
6	9	-1 (5.00)	+1 (100)	-1 (1.70)
7	10	-1 (5.00)	-1 (30.0)	+1 (3.20)
8	8	+1 (20.0)	+1 (100)	+1 (3.20)
9 (AP)	13	0 (12.5)	0 (65.0)	-1 (1.70)
10 (AP)	17	0 (12.5)	0 (65.0)	+1 (3.20)
11 (AP)	16	0 (12.5)	-1 (30.0)	0 (2.45)
12 (AP)	15	0 (12.5)	+1 (100)	0 (2.45)
13 (AP)	18	-1 (5.00)	0 (65.0)	0 (2.45)
14 (AP)	19	+1 (20.0)	0 (65.0)	0 (2.45)
15 (CP)	6	0 (12.5)	0 (65.0)	0 (2.45)
16 (CP)	4	0 (12.5)	0 (65.0)	0 (2.45)
17 (CP)	11	0 (12.5)	0 (65.0)	0 (2.45)
18 (CP)	7	0 (12.5)	0 (65.0)	0 (2.45)
19 (CP)	20	0 (12.5)	0 (65.0)	0 (2.45)
20 (CP)	14	0 (12.5)	0 (65.0)	0 (2.45)

^aPartial condenser cooling was applied during the Head-cut distillation only.

Table 2. Compounds groups, names, odor **description**, odor desirability, odor threshold and Heart cut maximum levels throughout CCD, and concentrations, standard deviation and significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between distillation fractions of the 6 RSM Center Point replicates) ^a.

Compound		Odor description	Odor desirability	Odor threshold	Heart-cut maximum levels of CCD	Fraction concentration		
Group	Name					Head-cut	Heart-1 cut	Heart-2 cut
Alcohol content	Ethanol (% v/v)	Alcoholic	-	-	71.0	87.7±0.4c	70.5±0.5b	55.2±1.4a
Head compounds	Acetaldehyde	Pungent	STB	25.0 ^b	171	839±102c	121±10b	9.68±0.64a
	Acetal	Fruity/Sherry	-	0.250 ^b	38.0	153±25c	25.5±1.7b	2.67±0.29a
	Ethyl acetate	Solvent	STB	12.5 ^c	35.4	227±34b	18.5±1.9a	3.72±0.43a
Fruity esters	Ethyl butyrate	Fruity	LTB	0.005 ^b	0.263	1.95±0.78	d. - n.q.	n.d.
	Ethyl hexanoate	Fruity	LTB	0.0013 ^b	0.956	2.20±0.98b	0.699±0.065a	d. - n.q.
	Ethyl octanoate	Fruity	LTB	0.0005 ^b	1.21	1.13±0.43b	0.980±0.113b	0.090±0.031a
	Ethyl decanoate	Floral/Brandy	LTB	0.105 ^d	0.14	0.520±0.092b	0.117±0.007a	0.087±0.024a
Tail compounds	Ethyl lactate	Lactic	-	25.0 ^b	28.7	0.396±0.112a	10.3±1.2b	35.6±3.6c
	Furfural	Burned	-	5.10 ^c	0.480	n.d.	d. - n.q.	0.600±0.056
	β-phenylethanol	Rose	-	2.50 ^b	2.00	0.149±0.024a	0.763±0.077b	2.62±0.26c
Terpenic compounds	Linalool	Floral/Muscat	LTB	0.250 ^e	2.43	0.197±0.017a	1.72±0.11c	0.576±0.028b
	α-terpineol	Floral	-	75.0 ^e	2.00	0.248±0.022a	1.78±0.18b	1.81±0.14b
Higher alcohols	1-hexanol	Mown grass	-	5.00 ^f	1.29	0.295±0.03a	1.26±0.09b	0.334±0.01a
	1-propanol	Fusel-like	-	208 ^b	51.5	26.3±4.7a	48.8±5.8b	38.1±3.5b
	2-methyl-1-butanol	Fusel-like	-	7.50 ^b	26.4	6.59±1.05a	25.8±2.5b	6.73±0.43a
	3-methyl-1-butanol	Fusel-like	-	7.50 ^b	168	41.9±5.2a	162±16c	55.3±3.8b
Others	Methanol	-	-	167 ^b , 200 ^g	92.2	108±18b	75.9±9.2a	99.5±10.6b
	Acetic acid	Vinegar-like	-	50.0 ^e	16.0	247±23b	9.67±0.84a	8.04±0.54a

^a Except ethanol (% v/v), all compounds are expressed in g/hL a.a. "d. - n.q." means detected in at least one replicate, but not quantified. "n.d." means no detected in any replicate. "-" means there is not enough information. "LTB" means Larger-The-Best. "STB" means Smaller-The-Best.

^b Referenced in Christoph & Bauer-Christoph (2007). ^c Referenced in Clutton & Evans (1978). ^d Referenced in Pino, Tolle, Gök & Winterhalter (2012). ^e Referenced in Cacho, Moncayo, Palma, Ferreira & Culleré (2012). ^f Referenced in Apostolopoulou, Flouros, Demertzis & Akrida-Demertzi (2005). ^g European legal limit (European Commission, 2008).

Table 3. Compounds Heart-cut concentration models. Significant regression coefficients values ($p < 0.05$) with their standard errors of linear (L), quadratic (^2) and 2-way interaction (-) effects by HTV, HDV, pH and CFR rescaled factors (± 1), and equation's adjusted correlation coefficient (R-adj) ^a.

Compound / Coefficient	Intercept	Block1	HTV (L)	HDV (L)	pH (L)	CFR (L)	HTV(^2)	HDV(^2)	pH(^2)	CFR(^2)	HTV-HDV	HTV-pH	HTV-CFR	HDV-pH	HDV-CFR	pH-CFR	R-adj
Ethanol (% v/v)	65.3 $\pm 0.1^*$	-0.14 ± 0.116	-3.90 $\pm 0.13^*$	-0.692 $\pm 0.148^*$	0.190 ± 0.148	n.s.	1.30 $\pm 0.22^*$	n.s.	-0.477 $\pm 0.227^*$	n.s.	-0.208 ± 0.179	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.986
Acetaldehyde	80.5 $\pm 1.3^*$	-4.38 $\pm 1.52^*$	-30.5 $\pm 1.8^*$	-24.6 $\pm 2.1^*$	7.86 $\pm 2.08^*$	-8.78 $\pm 2.08^*$	11.5 $\pm 3.1^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	8.29 $\pm 2.52^*$	n.s.	2.88 ± 2.52	4.35 $\pm 2.33^*$	n.s.	n.s.	0.972
Acetal	16.8 $\pm 0.5^*$	0.951 $\pm 0.534^*$	-7.04 $\pm 0.54^*$	-5.57 $\pm 0.64^*$	-1.75 $\pm 0.64^*$	-1.8 $\pm 0.64^*$	2.65 $\pm 0.94^*$	n.s.	3.85 $\pm 1.14^*$	-1.19 ± 1.14	1.93 $\pm 0.77^*$	n.s.	n.s.	-1.27 $\pm 0.71^*$	-0.982 ± 0.714	n.s.	0.952
Ethyl acetate	13.1 $\pm 0.5^*$	1.05 $\pm 0.54^*$	-4.44 $\pm 0.57^*$	-6.62 $\pm 0.67^*$	-2.56 $\pm 0.67^*$	-1.04 ± 0.67	1.66 ± 0.99	n.s.	2.99 $\pm 1.03^*$	n.s.	2.54 $\pm 0.81^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	-0.938 ± 0.748	1.41 $\pm 0.75^*$	0.933
Ethyl butyrate	0.091 $\pm 0.003^*$	0.014 $\pm 0.007^*$	-0.037 $\pm 0.008^*$	-0.062 $\pm 0.01^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.024 $\pm 0.012^*$	n.s.	n.s.	-0.017 ± 0.011	-0.017 ± 0.011	0.017 ± 0.011	0.832
Ethyl hexanoate	0.469 $\pm 0.014^*$	0.062 $\pm 0.016^*$	-0.155 $\pm 0.017^*$	-0.159 $\pm 0.02^*$	n.s.	0.030 ± 0.020	0.058 $\pm 0.03^*$	n.s.	-0.071 $\pm 0.031^*$	n.s.	0.052 $\pm 0.024^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	-0.041 $\pm 0.022^*$	0.063 $\pm 0.022^*$	0.930
Ethyl octanoate	0.67 $\pm 0.021^*$	0.133 $\pm 0.025^*$	-0.215 $\pm 0.03^*$	-0.133 $\pm 0.035^*$	n.s.	n.s.	0.081 ± 0.051	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.048 ± 0.042	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.067 ± 0.039	0.871
Ethyl decanoate	0.109 $\pm 0.001^*$	n.s.	-0.008 $\pm 0.003^*$	-0.005 ± 0.004	n.s.	-0.007 $\pm 0.004^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.005 ± 0.004	n.s.	n.s.	-0.005 ± 0.004	0.004 ± 0.004	0.005 ± 0.004	0.546
Ethyl lactate	20.0 $\pm 0.2^*$	-1.78 $\pm 0.26^*$	6.66 $\pm 0.31^*$	1.95 $\pm 0.36^*$	-1.74 $\pm 0.36^*$	n.s.	-2.62 $\pm 0.54^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	-0.958 $\pm 0.441^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.975
Furfural	0.313 $\pm 0.013^*$	n.s.	0.125 $\pm 0.018^*$	0.059 $\pm 0.021^*$	n.s.	n.s.	-0.049 ± 0.032	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.033 ± 0.026	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.796
β -phenylethanol	1.49 $\pm 0.01^*$	-0.133 $\pm 0.017^*$	0.512 $\pm 0.021^*$	0.116 $\pm 0.024^*$	n.s.	n.s.	-0.202 $\pm 0.036^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.051 ± 0.03	-0.032 ± 0.03	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.979
Linalool	1.3 $\pm 0.02^*$	-0.055 $\pm 0.019^*$	-0.321 $\pm 0.021^*$	-0.071 $\pm 0.024^*$	0.511 $\pm 0.024^*$	-0.043 $\pm 0.024^*$	0.12 $\pm 0.036^*$	n.s.	-0.077 $\pm 0.037^*$	n.s.	n.s.	-0.173 $\pm 0.029^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.029 ± 0.027	0.982
α -terpineol	1.82 $\pm 0.01^*$	-0.145 $\pm 0.017^*$	n.s.	0.067 $\pm 0.022^*$	-0.238 $\pm 0.022^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	-0.128 $\pm 0.034^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.918
1-hexanol	0.909 $\pm 0.006^*$	-0.045 $\pm 0.007^*$	-0.260 $\pm 0.009^*$	n.s.	0.012 ± 0.01	-0.011 ± 0.01	0.097 $\pm 0.015^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.985
1-propanol	45.1 $\pm 0.3^*$	-4.37 $\pm 0.35^*$	-3.13 $\pm 0.42^*$	n.s.	0.692 ± 0.491	-0.73 ± 0.491	1.06 ± 0.73	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	-0.706 ± 0.595	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.938
2-methyl-1-butanol	18.6 $\pm 0.2^*$	-1.43 $\pm 0.18^*$	-5.36 $\pm 0.22^*$	n.s.	0.401 ± 0.261	n.s.	2.00 $\pm 0.39^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.978
3-methyl-1-butanol	122 $\pm 1^*$	-10.0 $\pm 1.1^*$	-30.1 $\pm 1.4^*$	n.s.	2.47 ± 1.59	-1.91 ± 1.59	11.2 $\pm 2.4^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.976
Methanol	85.8 $\pm 0.5^*$	-8.42 $\pm 0.57^*$	6.36 $\pm 0.7^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	-1.48 $\pm 1.21^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	-1.23 ± 0.99	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.954
Acetic acid	9.49 $\pm 0.18^*$	0.396 ± 0.266	-0.689 $\pm 0.292^*$	-2.79 $\pm 0.34^*$	n.s.	-0.786 $\pm 0.341^*$	n.s.	1.03 $\pm 0.52^*$	n.s.	n.s.	1.19 $\pm 0.41^*$	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	0.857

^a Except ethanol, all compounds are expressed in g/hL a.a. HTV means the percentage (%) of Heart-2. HDV means Head-Cut Volume. CFR means Cooling Flow Rate. * $p < 0.001$; n.s. means no significant.

Table 4. Distillation conditions, desirability values and predicted and analytical composition of head off-flavors reduction; terpenic enhance and fruity esters enhance optimums calculated with RSM and desirability function approaches ^a.

<i>Distillation conditions</i>	Head off-flavor reduction	Terpenic enhance	Fruity Esters enhance	Head off-flavor reduction	Terpenic enhance	Fruity Esters enhance	Head off-flavor reduction	Terpenic enhance	Fruity Esters enhance
HTV (%)	100	16.7	66.7	100	16.7	66.7	100	16.7	66.7
HDV (mL)	20.0	20.0	5.00	20.0	20.0	5.00	20.0	20.0	5.00
pH	1.70	3.20	2.95	1.70	3.20	2.95	1.70	3.20	2.95
CFR (mL/min)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	<i>Predicted values (RSM) for Muscat 2015 heart cut</i>			<i>Analytical values for Muscat 2016 heart cut</i>			<i>Analytical values for Macabeo 2016 heart cut</i>		
Desirability value	0.993	0.806	0.658						
Ethanol (% v/v)	61.1	67.6	64.8	56.8 ±0.0 a	62.9 ±0.0 c	61.2 ±0.2 b	56.5 ±0.2 a	63.3 ±0.2 c	61.6 ±0.5 b
<i>Compounds (g/hL a.a.)</i>									
Acetaldehyde	27.1	77.4	88.0	15.5 ±0.3 a	24.9 ±3.1 b	37.1 ±2.6 c	21.5 ±0.6 a	50.5 ±3.2 b	63.7 ±3.8 c
Acetal	11.7	12.7	19.1	8.01 ±0.07 a	9.47 ±0.8 a	17.2 ±1.4 b	10.1 ±0.2 ab	7.38 ±0.01 a	14.2 ±2.7 b
Ethyl acetate	8.44	8.38	18.1	41.9 ±1 c	12.3 ±1.8 a	30.2 ±1.1 b	36.4 ±5.5 c	9.10 ±0.30 a	19.4 ±0.8 b
Ethyl butyrate	0.000	0.022	0.172	0.235 ±0.003 a	d.-n.q.	0.296 ±0.005 b	0.218 ±0.046	d.-n.q.	0.256 ±0.005
Ethyl hexanoate	0.119	0.386	0.648	1.06 ±0.03 b	0.800 ±0.008 a	1.25 ±0.03 c	0.848 ±0.056 b	0.706 ±0.027 a	1.19 ±0.01 c
Ethyl octanoate	0.287	0.751	0.795	1.50 ±0.01	1.53 ±0.06	1.50 ±0.14	1.16 ±0.02 a	1.33 ±0.13 a	1.64 ±0.02 b
Ethyl decanoate	0.097	0.104	0.106	0.319 ±0.054	0.450 ±0.077	0.330 ±0.048	0.203 ±0.037 a	0.252 ±0.013 a	0.338 ±0.014 b
Ethyl lactate	28.7	15.2	18.6	52.2 ±1.8 b	13.4 ±0.5 a	16.4 ±0.1 a	3.90 ±0.15 c	1.12 ±0.14 a	1.84 ±0.26 b
Furfural	0.480	0.244	0.279	d.-n.q.	d.-n.q.	d.-n.q.	d.-n.q.	n.d.	d.-n.q.
β-phenylethanol	2.00	1.17	1.50	3.93 ±0.21 b	2.76 ±0.2 a	3.00 ±0.06 a	2.85 ±0.02 b	1.97 ±0.17 a	2.18 ±0.03 a
Linalool	0.543	2.03	1.52	0.128 ±0.003 a	2.17 ±0.14 c	1.62 ±0.03 b	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
Geraniol	d.-n.q.	d.-n.q.	d.-n.q.	n.d.	0.273 ±0.013 b	0.185 ±0.001 a	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
α-terpineol	2.00	1.52	1.54	1.01 ±0.06	0.977 ±0.027	0.944 ±0.002	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
1-hexanol	0.723	1.13	0.831	0.840 ±0.032 a	1.14 ±0.05 b	0.886 ±0.004 a	1.37 ±0.05 a	1.94 ±0.12 b	1.56 ±0.07 a
1-propanol	42.4	48.1	43.8	24.8 ±0.3 a	27.9 ±0.8 b	25.3 ±0.3 a	18.6 ±0.1	21.2 ±1.3	19.2 ±0.6
2-methyl-1-butanol	14.9	23.5	17.3	35.0 ±0.8 a	49.2 ±2 b	38.5 ±0.1 a	19.0 ±0.8 a	27.0 ±1.9 b	21.8 ±0.7 a
3-methyl-1-butanol	99.1	148	113	133 ±2 a	179 ±7 b	142 ±0 a	121 ±4 a	166 ±11 b	135 ±5 a
Methanol	89.2	79.7	85.9	47.9 ±0.8 b	44.2 ±0.6 a	46 ±0.9 ab	44.4 ±0.8	41.8 ±2.4	41.5 ±1.1
Acetic acid	7.46	6.62	11.9	9.98 ±1.18	8.08 ±1.08	10.7 ±0.8	9.17 ±0.61	8.77 ±1.46	11.4 ±0.4

^a Optimal distillation conditions and desirability values were calculated using the responses in bold. "n.d." means no detected. "d.-n.q." means detected but **not** quantified.

1 Figure Graphics

2 Figure 1.

3

4

Figure 2.

5

6

Supplementary Material

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